

PRELIMINARY RESULTS FROM AN AFTU PROTOTYPE BASED ON SMART AVIONICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development and testing of an Autonomous Flight Termination Unit (AFTU) within the SAFEST project framework. Traditional flight termination systems rely heavily on ground-based infrastructure, which limits flexibility, incurs high costs, and introduces delays due to human decision-making. The proposed AFTU leverages advances in GNSS technology, onboard computational capabilities, and avionics software platforms to enable real-time, autonomous termination decisions. The unit is highly configurable, allowing range safety officers to define mission-specific rules and integrate proprietary software to meet varying national regulations across Europe.

The paper focuses on the initial prototype's test campaign that Sener is developing in the frame of the RD EC Horizon Europe programme., detailing the system architecture, test setup, and performance results. It also outlines the roadmap toward flight qualification, emphasizing the system's adaptability for different launchers and regulatory environments.

Index Terms— launchers, flight safety, flight termination, EGSE, test campaign

1. INTRODUCTION

The traditional flight termination approach involves a complex interaction between the launcher, the ground systems and their operators. This interaction brings a dependence on the availability of ground infrastructures that are directly related to the start cadence can have an impact. Also intervening humans as a potential source of delays (typically 3-5 seconds reaction time) in intervention during flight. The inclusion of the ground segment in the safety chain of the launcher flight also has a direct impact on the cost since their use implies an important fee.

An Autonomous Flight Termination System (AFTS) consists in the entire logic behind the decision-making (safety systems, ground infrastructure and human decision-

maker) as an unmanned system on-board the launcher, as depicted in the following figure. This can increase the launch cadence, since several launchers can be operated practically at the same time, and independently of the supporting aviation safety infrastructure on the ground.

The AFTS is an independent, redundant system on board the launcher, which must function despite a failure of the carrier avionics. The system is completely decoupled from functional avionics and has its own positioning system, sensors and power sources. Accordingly, it can be developed as an independent system and used on a wide variety of launchers. The AFTU provides the termination signal to the actuator, whereby the flight termination can be achieved either via thrust scheduling or targeted explosion.

Following table shows a comparison between the different elements necessary to operate the different types of termination systems.

Table 1. AFTS vs FTS elements comparison

Traditional FTS	AFTS
Flight systems	
HW Unit	
	Safe & Arm
	Ordnance
Receiver	-
FTS logic box	-
Battery	-
UHF antenna	-
Hybrid coupler	-
Metric Tracking sources (RCC 324)	
	GPS
	L-band antenna
	Couplers
	Power distribution box
	Vehicle battery
Telemetry encoder	-
Telemetry transmitter	-
S-band antenna	-
-	IMU/INS
-	Flight computer
-	External tracking inputs

Radar transponder	
Transponder	-
C-band antenna	-
Hybrid coupler	-
Power distribution box	-
Vehicle battery	-
Ground systems	
Command transmitters	
Power supplies	-
Antennas	-
Amplifiers	-
Telemetry receivers	
Antenna	-
Decoders	-
Ground comm networks	-
Radars	
Radar sites	-
Ground comm networks	-
Timing infrastructure	-
Mission flight control	
MFCO	-
Telemetry officer	-
Certified display	-
Others	
Preflight testing	-

1.1. Motivation

Traditional termination systems are costly and complex, and also, they jeopardize the increase of the launch cadence. Introducing AFTS will provide following benefits to the launcher providers:

- Decrease of recurrent price per launch, due to the removal of complex equipment and ground stations.
- Increase of cadence since no dedicate ground stations and officer are required.
- Increase of operations, avoiding limitations from the use of ground stations (e.g. line-of-sight constraints).

Fig. 1. AFTS main advantages schematic

In order to design an AFTS system, following main requirements should be taken into account, which have been

extracted from relevant actors in the European sector (e.g. launch providers, range officers, space agencies):

- Drastic reduction of SWaP and cost of the on-board equipment.
- High-reliability, mainly achieved by HW design avoiding any single point failure (including protection against external interferences), and by the maximum SW category (i.e. SW Cat. A from ECSS).
- Compatibility with current traditional flight termination systems, since these units would not be operated till fully certified, including dedicated flight campaigns.
- Availability to customize the termination logic, which the possibility to include own proprietary SW, which may not be possible to be shared with the AFTS manufacturer due to export control restrictions.
- Scalability to different launch sizes or needs. The AFTS solution should be designed for small launchers, with the capability to be extended to greater launch sizes.

1.2. SAFEST project

SAFEST is proposing an Autonomous Flight Termination System design and architecture that is highly customizable by the user, to cover different countries regulations, and to adapt to different launcher types, without the need of a new development.

In particular, the project is focused on the development of a AFTU unit, the equipment that executes the termination logic taking the data from the tracking inputs. The objective of the project is to reach a TRL 5-6 for the AFTU SW and the avionics.

Fig. 2. SAFEST project consortium

2. AFTU DESIGN

The architecture of the AFTU demonstrator defines the main functional blocks and data flow that enable the autonomous evaluation of flight safety conditions. The first part of this section provides an overview of the core components and their interactions. Additionally, the mission rules algorithms that are available to check the safety rules are itemized.

2.1. High-level architecture

The high-level architecture of the SAFEST unit is illustrated in Fig. 3. Each unit integrates an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receiver. Data from these sensors are fused in the onboard data fusion module to provide a robust and continuous navigation solution. The GNSS measurements are processed within a loosely coupled Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) framework, enabling reliable state estimation even under partial GNSS availability [2].

This solution will be provided to the mission rules so that they can check the violation of the mission rules. Note that the mission rules will also receive data from external tracking inputs and redundant unit (cross-strap interface) to perform the check of the mission rules violation. The communication is completed with the housekeeping telemetry to the Ground Support Equipment (GSE) and the On-Board Computer (OBC).

Fig. 3. SAFEST unit architecture

There are two main phases involved in the operation of an AFTU, (i) missionization and (ii) flight. The SAFEST unit architecture defines the electrical physical inputs and outputs of the unit. These I/O connections enable full user configuration during the missionization phase.

- Master and logic arm
- Liftoff indicator
- Fail-safe system enabling

The following table provides a more detailed description of key features of the AFTU unit design proposed

Table 2. SAFEST unit design key features

Feature	Description
Cross-Strapped Interface	To increase the reliability of the AFTS, SAFEST unit can operate in cross-strap redundancy. The following information will be transmitted between the units: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fail-safe inhibiting signal • Health Status
Fail-Safe System	The Fail-Safe system monitors the power input and generates the termination command in case a power failure is detected. The Fail-Safe system can be enabled/disabled by the user and is inhibited in the scenario where the Fail-Safe system of the redundant unit is enabled and operating correctly.
Mission Rules Config.	The behavior of the mission rules can be configured by the user to its full extent by means of a configuration file. Note that the mission rules SW will be provided to the user in an open format, therefore the user can configure any new mission rule.
Integrated Navigation Solution	The baseline unit includes a low-cost hybrid navigation solution that provides robust estimation of the position and velocity of the vehicle at high frequency. Besides, it provides accurate acceleration and angular velocity estimations, necessary to detect faulty events (e.g. vehicle tumbling).
External Tracking Inputs	The mission rules can manage up to three external tracking inputs provided by the user. Three types of interfaces are envisaged: INS, GNSS and hybrid interface.

2.2. Mission rules algorithms

Mission rules (MR) are a predefined set of conditions that must be met throughout the vehicle's flight to ensure that the launch is conducted in a safe manner. These rules are configured by the user prior to flight and are continuously evaluated on board the vehicle during the mission.

The mission rules logic execution involves a sequence of tasks to ensure accurate estimations and real-time assessment:

- Processing the tracking inputs information and performing cross-checks when necessary.
- Updating the vehicle's state vector based on the processed tracking information.
- Evaluating the current state against the predefined mission rules to detect any violations.

The unit is also designed with a flexible and scalable architecture in terms of sensor management. It is capable to

manage multiple tracking inputs in parallel. This wide margin enables the integration of various external sensor—such as IMU, INS, or GNSS— as well as the hybrid navigation solution coming from the navigation partition.

Once the most reliable solution is selected, the mission rules SW must estimate a set of variables, known as the state vector. They can be related to:

- *Vehicle*: non-gravitational acceleration, angular velocity, lift-off flag, ...
- *Trajectory*: position, velocity, IIP coordinates, downrange, ...
- *Orbit*: semi-major axis, eccentricity, inclination, is in orbit flag, ...

The state vector variables are exposed to the user to customize and define launch safety conditions. This capability enables one of the most important features of the mission rules SW, its highly configurability. As a result, users can adapt the unit to different launch vehicles and spaceports with minimal effort.

The user could cover all the safety requirements using the following mission rules algorithms because they perform a wide range of checks.

- User defined check
- Table check
- Gate check
- Boundary check
- Tumbling check
- Green time

The execution of the mission rules can trigger the following outputs:

- Safe Condition (SC)
- End of Responsibility (EoR)
- Warning (W)
- Terminate (T)

Fig. 4 recapitulates the process followed during the MR execution. Several conditions that ensure a safe flight are defined, and, subsequently, associated with a safe or termination purpose.

By combining different rule types, specific mission constraints can be checked. For instance, a typical configuration may include a termination if the monitoring of the ground track or the IIP determines that will fall out of allowed areas. In contrast, the safe condition flag, or even an end of responsibility, is activated if the launcher leaves the corridor crossing a gate that guarantees the safety of the flight.

This demonstrates that the modularity of the mission rules algorithms allows users to compose the safety logic to diverse launch scenarios and regulatory frameworks.

Fig. 4. Mission rules logic

3. METHODOLOGY FOR TEST CAMPAIGN

The SAFEST validation process follows a structured and progressive approach, transitioning from simulation to real hardware environment. This methodology ensures that navigation algorithms and mission rules are rigorously verified across increasing levels of system realism prior to final integration, enabling a robust and reliable transition from development to final hardware integration.

Validation began with simulations, where algorithm models were tested in ideal conditions to verify functional correctness and conduct unit testing of key components such as the Instantaneous Impact Point (IIP) and boundary check logic. The next stage translated these models into embedded C-code to validate auto-coding integrity and consistency with initial results. Hardware-in-the-loop stages introduced real-time execution on the target processor, enabling verification of both functional behavior and physical interfaces with simulated sensors and actuators. Particular attention was paid to data synchronization from heterogeneous sensors like IMU and GNSS.

Fig. 5. Validation process approach

3.1. HIL Prototype

This paper shows the results coming from the HIL step. All tests are carried out with the same setup since the changes between each one are made through software. In every case, the prototype is setup with the real sensors, and it is also connected to the EGSE which generates all required signals to simulate the trajectory.

The SAFEST Prototype is composed of three elements: 2 sensors and the processing board. These sensors are connected directly through a serial connection to the board. The processing board is a Zedboard exposing a Zynq-7000 processor hosting the AFTU software.

Fig. 6. SAFEST Prototype

4. TEST CAMPAIGN

The validation of the AFTU prototype has been carried through a structured test campaign thought up to assess the performance of the system under nominal condition and injection failures.

The objective of the campaign is to verify and validate the implementation of the mission rules logic, as well as the integration between mission rules and navigation partition. Tests were executed in a HIL environment, presented in the previous section, to achieve a representative environment. The following subsections present the test plan, the results and detailed analysis of selected test cases.

4.1. Test Plan

A test plan has been prepared to carry out a structured validation campaign. The test cases created are described in Table 3 and they outline the scenarios simulated to evaluate the performance of the model. The description cell details

the objective of the test, and, if applicable, which trajectories present faults injection into the nominal trajectory.

Table 3. Test cases definition

Test Name	Description
<i>Nominal Andøya</i>	Nominal mission rules (MR) are executed to demonstrate that no termination flags are triggered.
<i>Nominal Bowen</i>	Nominal MR executed to demonstrate that no termination flags are triggered.
<i>Nominal Kourou</i>	Nominal MR executed to demonstrate that no termination flags are triggered.
<i>Corridor Exit</i>	Checking that the exit gate is crossed triggering a EoR, before reaching orbit.
<i>Boundary IIP</i>	The IIP projection is forced to fall within a forbidden region to detect the SC flag.
<i>Boundary GT</i>	The ground track is forced to fall within a forbidden region and leaves the flight corridor. A SC and a terminate shall be detected.
<i>Engine Loss</i>	An engine loss is simulated after detecting lift-off (LO) to detect a terminate. <i>Trajectory with failures.</i>
<i>Engine Failure</i>	The nga is perturbed to trigger different effects and check that the termination flag is raised. <i>Trajectory with failures.</i>
<i>Tracking Input Loss</i>	A termination shall be triggered due to the reception of no valid navigation data. <i>Trajectory with failures in navigation data.</i>
<i>Hierarchy</i>	The same condition is used to generate a SC and a terminate, the hierarchy of the model is tested expecting a SC.
<i>Gates Combination</i>	Intermediate gate checks are performed to trigger different warnings flags.

4.2. Test results

The following table presents the results of the test campaign, categorizing the test based on their outcomes. Each test has been labeled as 'passed', 'partly passed' or 'fail' based on performance. Further analyses are provided to explain partial outcomes.

Overall, the results show a high success rate, with minor issues observed in two of the cases.

Table 4. Categorization of test results

Test Result	Test Cases
Passed Test	Nominal Bowen, Nominal Kourou, Corridor Exit, Boundary GT, Engine Loss, Engine Failure, Hierarchy, Tracking Input Loss, Gates Combination
Partly Passed Test	Nominal Andøya, Boundary IIP
Fail Test	–

4.3. Test cases analysis

This section will mainly focus on reviewing the test cases categorized as partly passed, analyzing and providing the reasons behind the partial success. At the same time, a couple of tests successful completed will be summarize.

4.3.1. Nominal Andøya

Nominal Andøya test case has been categorized as ‘partly passed’. The nominal cases have two clear objectives: no termination flags shall be triggered, and a permanent SC shall be reached before exceeding the flight corridor—see Fig. 8—.

Fig. 7. Nominal Andøya scenario

Fig. 8. Safe Condition flags in nominal Andøya scenario

Although both conditions have been met, the warning signals are not correctly generated—see Fig. 9—. In this test case only one gate can generate a warning flag when the IIP projection crosses the gate. However, there are two identical flags spaced a few seconds apart. This would indicate that the IIP moves forward until it crosses the gate, then moves backward and passes the gate again. This behavior is not the normal one.

This behavior is justified by two factors:

1. The IIP is a position and velocity-dependent calculation
2. The EGSE simulations use real interfaces and sensors that have intrinsic error.

Since the error occurs in parallel with the first stage separation, the measured acceleration temporarily becomes negative instead of staying at 0 m/s², causing a brief deceleration and resulting in the gate being crossed twice.

Therefore, after having identified this failure, it is proposed to modify the conditions parameter to evaluate the ground track in all nominal cases instead of the impact point.

Fig. 9. Warning flags in nominal Andøya scenario

4.3.2. Boundary IIP

Boundary IIP test case has been categorized as ‘partly passed’. The main objective of this scenario is to verify that

the algorithms can detect when the IIP projection is falling over a forbidden boundary—see Fig. 10—.

Fig. 10. Boundary IIP scenario

Fig. 11. Safe condition flags in boundary IIP scenario

This case was chosen to evaluate the tumbling algorithm, but it did not report the expected result. Due to sensor errors, the EGSE registers a higher velocity than the simulator, causing the launcher to exit the tumbling region too early without reporting a warning signal. The suggested solution to deal with this issue is to modify the parameters of the conditions to ensure that the tumbling warning is going to rise.

4.3.3. Engine Failure

Engine Failure test case has been categorized as 'passed'. Its goal is to simulate trajectories with failures by perturbing the acceleration. In the simulator a Montecarlo analysis were carried out, and, to replicate it, four opposite test case has been created. The results attached correspond to a perturbation in the y-axis at the beginning of the simulation, the acceleration takes a positive and large value, which

results in a lateral deviation of the trajectory to the right side—see Fig. 12—.

Fig. 12. Result of the perturbed trajectory

The simulation triggers a termination signal which means that the failure has been identified—see Fig. 13—. In this case, it corresponds to a boundary terminate flag, the IIP exceed the flight corridor. The rest of the outcomes show the expected behavior, it is concluded that the purpose of the test has been fulfilled.

Fig. 13. Termination flag in engine failure scenario

4.3.4. Gates Combination

Gates combination test case is categorized as 'passed'. Its purpose is to monitor if the vehicle crosses designated gates at the correct time. The scenario includes three moving gates (pink) and two fixed gates (blue)—see Fig. 14—.

Fig. 14. Gates combination scenario

The lower-latitude gates confirm that the vehicle goes over them within the predefined interval time, while the blue gates advise that the IIP is nears the flight corridor—see Fig. 15—.

Fig. 15. Warning flag in gates combination scenario

5. ROADMAP

The primary objective of the SAFEST project is to develop an AFTU prototype reaching TRL 5/6. Advancing to TRL 8/9 will require further maturation of the system and comprehensive system-level qualification campaign.

The current AFTU prototype has been designed to meet the baseline requirements and serves as a reference for the capabilities expected from an operational unit. The proposed development roadmap follows a two-step process: first, identification and maturation of missing technologies, and second, system-level testing and qualification including ground and flight campaigns.

Next step is the development of an engineering model, which will undergo extensive hardware-level ground testing.

Subsequently, a qualification model will integrate flight representative components, being used in the first flight test campaign. The unit will fly as a non-critical payload, either on a sounding rocket or a fighter aircraft.

Based on the results of this campaign, a flight model will be developed. This version will undergo a shadow flight test, integrated into a launch vehicle but not participating in the safety chain, as a final step before operational deployment.

Finally, the roadmap foresees independent verification and validation (V&V) activities by an external entity to strengthen the robustness and reliability of the system.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A more affordable access to space in terms of cost and flexibility is mandatory to meet users and market demands. A distinctive solution in this direction is the AFTS, which performs safety operations on-board the launch vehicle.

This paper has presented the development of the AFTU demonstrator, with a particular focus on the test campaign, providing a description of the test equipment and the test plan followed.

Since the objective is the development of the first European AFTU device, the design of the unit is driven by the user needs and the ability to be adapted to different regulations and constraints easily. The main results obtained in the first sections are:

- The proposed AFTU prototype and AFTS architecture is cheaper, more flexible and allows higher launch cadence than traditional FTS.
- Main features of SAFEST design, allowing to have a highly configurable and scalable design to different local regulations and launchers.

On the other hand, the fully integrated prototype has been successfully tested, demonstrating the reliability of the implemented algorithms.

The test campaign has enabled to determine the impact of integrating hardware components, which introduced bias and offsets causing deviations from simulated results, but it has been beneficial to identify bugs and refine the test campaign. Next steps of the development roadmap include the preparation of a functional EM after demonstrating the maturity of the system. With this objective, Sener has led an industrial consortium that have recently won an ESA project, called LoCRAFTS, devoted to further derisk AFTS technologies.

The work presented in this paper has been carried out in the frame of the SAFEST Project, where Sener is the coordinator of a joint effort of many individuals and organizations. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082662.

7. REFERENCES

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